

Wikidata data model for Natural History type specimens

Siobhan Leachman
Wikimedian in Residence
New Zealand Bioeconomy Science Institute
ORCID: [0000-0002-5398-7721](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5398-7721)
5 March 2026

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.18880276](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18880276)

[Image](#) of the [holotype specimen](#) of *Odontria cassiniae* held at the New Zealand Arthropod Collection.
Manaaki Whenua – Landcare Research, [CC BY 3.0](#), via Wikimedia Commons

Reuse Licence Statement: © Siobhan Leachman. Unless indicated otherwise for specific images, this document is licensed for reuse under the [Creative Commons Zero 1.0 licence](#). Please note that this licence does not apply to any images. Those specific images may be re-used as indicated in the image rights statement near the image. In essence, you are free to copy, distribute and adapt this document, so long as you abide by the other licence terms.

Table of Contents

[Motivation](#)

[Natural history type specimen data model](#)

[Item label and description](#)

[Wikidata item label](#)

[Item description](#)

[Wikidata properties](#)

[Instance of](#)

[Image](#)

[Reference illustration](#)

[Collection](#)

[Inventory number](#)

[Collection date](#)

[Location collected](#)

[Coordinate location](#)

[Nomenclatural type of](#)

[Collector](#)

[Specimen classifier](#)

[Described by source](#)

[Described at URL](#)

[Significant event](#)

[Sex or gender](#)

[Biological phase](#)

[Commons category](#)

[Identifiers generated for the specimen](#)

[iNaturalist observation id](#)

[DiSSCo DOI](#)

[GBIF occurrence identifier](#)

[GenBank](#)

[Exemplar Wikidata items](#)

[Wikidata type specimen item, its photograph and illustration](#)

[Future extensions to data model](#)

[Basis of Record](#)

[Biocultural notices](#)

[Preservation method](#)

[Other related links](#)

[Acknowledgements](#)

Motivation

The aim of this proposed Wikidata data model for Natural History type specimens is to support both the Galleries, Libraries, Archives and Museum (GLAM), Research, and Wiki communities in the creation of consistent, machine-readable data representing **notable** specimens and their associated collection events, collectors, determiners, and taxonomic determinations. This encourages related GLAM-held material to be appropriately linked to those Wikidata items thus helping to build a richer biodiversity information ecosystem, both within and external to the Wikiverse.

This data model draws heavily from existing documentation and data models, particularly the TDWG Biodiversity Information Standards Association DarwinCore standard <https://dwc.tdwg.org/> as well as Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) infrastructure and guiding documentation.

Natural history type specimen data model

Item label and description

Wikidata item label

The recommended Wikidata item label is “holotype of xxx” where xxx is the basionym or the original taxonomic name the holotype specimen acts as a reference for. This label describes the item in a translatable manner and is easily understood by a layperson.

Darwin Core equivalence: [dwc:identification](#)

It is recommended that the institution inventory number for the specimen be added as an alias i.e. in the “also known as” section of the Wikidata item.

Darwin Core equivalence: [dwc:catalogNumber](#)

Where other categories of type specimen hurdle the Wikidata notability requirements, the recommended Wikidata item label for such specimens should be “lectotype of xxx” or “neotype of xxx” etc where xxx is the species or subspecies name. It is recommended that xxx should be the basionym or original name of the species or subspecies.

Example item: <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q137825313>

Item description

The recommended format of the description of such items is as follows: “xxx (holotype, syntype, paratype, lectotype, paralectotype, neotype or allotype) specimen of xxx (full scientific name) held at xxx (institution) (institution inventory number)”.

Example item: <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q137825313>

Darwin Core equivalence: [dwc:identification](#)
[dwc:catalogNumber](#)

Wikidata properties

Instance of

[Instance of](#) (P31) [holotype](#) (Q1061403), [syntype](#) (Q719822), [paratype](#) (Q926578), [lectotype](#) (Q2439719), [paralectotype](#) (Q19353473), [neotype](#) (Q3874702), or [allotype](#) (Q19353437)

The “instance of” (P31) statement is required as, along with “subclass of” (P279), this statement is fundamental to Wikidata’s ontology and helps distinguish between an individual item and a category of items. An “instance of” statement should be as specific and accurate as possible.

The above “instance of” (P31) statement provides information on the specific kind of type specimen for which the Wikidata item is being created.

Example item: <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q137825313>

Darwin Core equivalence: [dwc:typeStatus](#) (Wikidata item for type of type specimen)

[Instance of](#) (P31) [material entity](#) (Q53617407), [preserved specimen](#) (Q137936990), [fossil specimen](#) (Q137937301), [living specimen](#) (Q137937392), [sample](#) (Q485146), [occurrence](#) (Q1190554), [human observation](#) (Q137937616), [machine observation](#) (Q137937752), [taxon](#) (Q16521), [occurrence](#) (Q1190554), [material citation](#) (Q137938025)

This “instance of” (P31) statement is needed to provide data on the basis of the record for the type specimen. This data statement helps describe the physical nature of the data record using Wikidata items that align with controlled vocabulary terms as set out by the Darwin Core standard.

Example item: <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q137825313>

Darwin Core equivalence: [dwc:basisOfRecord](#) (Wikidata item for nature of type specimen record)

Image

[Image](#) (P18) image of type specimen in Wikimedia Commons

Example item: <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q137825313>

Reference illustration

[Reference illustration](#) (P13162) illustration of type specimen in Wikimedia Commons

This property empowers the illustration of the type specimen to be linked to the type specimen Wikidata item. The structured data on Wikimedia Commons added to the illustration file can include a depicts statement linking to the holotype Wikidata item. By adding this value to a holotype specimen Wikidata item the Biodiversity Heritage Library [structured data on commons data model for scientific illustrations](#) is aligned to this model.

Example item: <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q137830487>

Collection

[Collection](#) (P195) Wikidata item for parent institution of collection
[object of statement has role](#) (P3831) → [holding institution](#) (Q131597993) [recommended]

[Collection](#) (P195) Wikidata item for collection (see [GRSciColl](#))
[object of statement has role](#) (P3831) → [holding collection](#) (Q137935182) [recommended]

Example item: <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q136936057>

Darwin core equivalence: [dwc:collectionID](#) (Wikidata item for collection)
[dwc:institutionID](#) [holding institution](#) (Q131597993)

Inventory number

[Inventory number](#) (P217) institution inventor number
[collection](#) (P195) → Wikidata item for collection (see [GRSciColl](#)) [recommended]

Example item: <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q136936057>

Darwin Core equivalence: [dwc:catalogNumber](#) institution inventor number
[dwc:collectionID](#) (Wikidata item for collection)

Collection date

[Collection date](#) (P14027) date of collection of specimen

Example item: <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q137825313>

Darwin Core equivalence: [dwc:eventDate](#) date of collection of specimen

Location collected

[Location collected](#) (P14117)

[object named as](#): text string for specific location if no Wikidata item [recommended]

Example item: <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q136936057>

Darwin Core equivalence: [dwc:locality](#) Wikidata item for locality of specimen collection

Coordinate location

[Coordinate location](#) (P625) number string of coordinates

[object of statement has role](#) (P3831) → [location collected](#) [recommended]

Example item: <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q136832210>

Darwin Core equivalence: [dwc:decimalLatitude](#), [dwc:decimalLongitude](#) number string for coordinates

Decimal latitude and decimal longitude are concatenated with a comma space that is the delimiter value, to create the location coordinates that can then be uploaded into Wikidata.

Nomenclatural type of

[nomenclatural type of](#) (P13478) Wikidata item for species

[subject has role](#) (P2868) → [holotype](#) (Q1061403), [syntype](#) (Q719822), [paratype](#) (Q926578), [lectotype](#) (Q2439719), [paralectotype](#) (Q19353473), [neotype](#) (Q3874702), [allotype](#) (Q19353437) [recommended]

It is possible that one type specimen can be the nomenclatural type of multiple species taxa.

Example item: <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q136936057>

Collector

[Collector](#) (P13914)

Wikidata item for collector of specimen

Ideally this should link to either people or ships although sometimes organisations may be appropriate.

Example item: <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q137825313>

Darwin Core equivalence: [dwc:recordedByID](#) Wikidata item for the specimen collector

Specimen classifier

[Specimen classifier](#) (P14026)

Wikidata item for the specimen determiner

[point in time](#) (P585) → date of determination [recommended]

Example item: <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q136936057>

Darwin Core equivalence: [dwc:identifiedByID](#) Wikidata item for the specimen determiner

[dwc:dateIdentified](#) Date of determination

Described by source

[Described by source](#) (P1343)

Wikidata item for publications describing the type specimen

[page\(s\)](#) (P304) → page in source describing holotype [optional]

[object of statement has role](#) (P3831) → [first valid description](#) (Q1361864), [recombination](#) (Q14594740), [nomenclatural act](#) (Q56027914), [taxon redescription](#) (Q42696902), [revision](#) (Q2146881), [taxonomic treatment](#) (Q32945461) [optional]

Example item: <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q137825361>

Dublin Core equivalence: [dcterms:references](#) Wikidata item for published source

Described at URL

[Described at URL](#) (P973) URLs linking to digital sources describing the type specimen
[language of work or name](#) (P407) → language of website [recommended]

It is recommended that, if possible, a link to the institution's collection record be added via this property.

If possible, a link to the GBIF occurrence record is also recommended. Currently (January 2026) there is no property for the GBIF occurrence identifier as this identifier is regarded by the Wikidata community as not being unique nor stable. To ensure the type specimen Wikidata item is connected to the GBIF occurrence record for that specimen (if one exists) it is highly recommended that the URL for that record be added to the Wikidata item using the "described at URL" property.

Example item: <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q137830487>

Dublin Core equivalence: [dcterms:references](#) text string giving URL reference

Significant event

[Significant event](#) Wikidata item for significant event eg a research expedition

Example item: <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q137825313>

Darwin Core equivalence: [dwc:eventID](#) Wikidata item for significant event

Sex or gender

[Sex or gender](#) (P21) [Female organism](#) (Q43445), [Male organism](#) (Q44148) or [Hermaphrodite](#) (Q303479)

Example item: <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q137825361>

Darwin Core equivalence: [dwc:sex](#) Wikidata item for female organism, male organism or hermaphrodite.

Biological phase

[Biological phase](#) (P4775) Wikidata item for the appropriate life stage of the specimen. For example [zygote](#) (Q170145), [egg](#) (Q17147), [larva](#) (Q129270), [pupa](#) (Q170595), [juvenile](#) (Q1516282), [adult](#) (Q80994), [seedling](#) (Q1385709)

Example item: <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q137825361>

Darwin Core equivalence: [dwc:lifeStage](#) Wikidata item for the appropriate life stage of the specimen

Commons category

[Commons category](#) (P373) link to the Wikimedia Commons category for images of the type specimen.

The Wikimedia Commons category should be added if one exists for the type specimen itself.

Example item: <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q137851491>

Identifiers generated for the specimen

Wikidata properties have been or may be created for identifiers relating to type specimens in other websites and databases. If properties for other databases have NOT been created a link to the appropriate URL can be added via the “described at URL” link. If an appropriate Wikidata property for a third party identifier does exist that type specimen identifier can be added to the type specimen Wikidata item.

Examples of Wikidata properties that link database identifiers to type specimen Wikidata items include:

iNaturalist observation id

[iNaturalist observation ID](#) (P5683) text string for the iNaturalist observation ID

Example item: <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q137851491>

Darwin Core equivalence: [dwc:occurrenceID](#) An occurrence identifier from a database

DiSSCo DOI

[DOI](#) (P356) text string for DOI minted by

This is an example of a digital extended specimen identifier generated by the initiative DiSSCo (<https://www.dissco.eu/>). DiSSCo aims to provide a DOI for all individual digital specimens in European natural history collections.

Example item: <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q137849910>

Darwin Core equivalence: [dwc:digitalspecimenID](#) An identifier for a particular instance of a Digital Specimen

Examples of identifiers where currently no Wikidata property exists:

GBIF occurrence identifier

[Described at URL](#) (P973) URLs linking to GBIF occurrence webpage
[language of work or name](#) (P407) → language of website

As currently there is no GBIF occurrence ID property in Wikidata (see below in the Future extensions to data model section for a discussion relating to this) the appropriate method to link to this data is via the URL for the GBIF occurrence record.

Example item: <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q136831989>

GenBank

[Described at URL](#) (P973) URLs linking to the US National Institute of Health GenBank (genetic sequence database)
[language of work or name](#) (P407) → language of website

This is an example of a genetic sequence database with identifiers that does not currently have a Wikidata property related to it. As such the appropriate method to link to this data is via the URL for the genetic sequence record in the database.

Example item: <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q137855885>

Exemplar Wikidata items

<https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q136936057> holotype of a moth, holotype for two species names

<https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q136831989> holotype of a beetle

<https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q137825361> holotype of a beetle

<https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q137825313> holotype of a starfish

<https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q137851491> holotype of fungus gnat with links to iNaturalist observation id

<https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q137855885> holotype specimen of a fungi species with iNaturalist observation id and links to RNA & DNA sequencing

<https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q137849910> holotype of spider with DiSSCO DOI and with more data on collector and date of collection than DiSSCO and Collection Management System record.

Wikidata type specimen item, its photograph and illustration

What follows is a practical example where the data models are used to connect the type specimen, its digitized image file and natural history illustration in Wikidata and Wikimedia Commons.

<https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q137830487> Wikidata holotype specimen item.

[https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Preserved_colours_of_Haplochromis_argens_male_holotype_\(RMNH.PISC.83588\)_-ZooKeys-256-001-g005.jpeg](https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Preserved_colours_of_Haplochromis_argens_male_holotype_(RMNH.PISC.83588)_-ZooKeys-256-001-g005.jpeg) Wikimedia Commons image file of holotype specimen with structured data following the natural history specimen data model.

[https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Haplochromis_argens_male_holotype,_RMNH.PISC.83588\)_-ZooKeys-256-001-g002.jpeg](https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Haplochromis_argens_male_holotype,_RMNH.PISC.83588)_-ZooKeys-256-001-g002.jpeg) Wikimedia Commons image file of illustration of holotype specimen with structured data following the Biodiversity Heritage Library data model for scientific illustrations.

Future extensions to data model

Basis of Record

Currently the basis of record data is modelled as an “instance of” statement. However ideally a new Wikidata property should be proposed to describe the specific nature of the data record. This would continue the alignment of this data model with the Darwin Core data standard. See [dwc:basisofRecord](http://dwc.basisofRecord).

Biocultural notices

The writers of this documentation discussed proposing a Wikidata property for biocultural notices (<https://localcontexts.org/notice/bc-notice/>) to aid the inclusion of Biocultural Notices to the type specimen data model. From July 2025 GBIF is piloting a project testing the application of Local Contexts Traditional Knowledge and Biocultural Labels to GBIF occurrence records. For more information see <https://localcontexts.org/gbif-pilot-using-tk-and-bc-labels/>.

Discussions have been taking place about the application of Biocultural Notices amongst the wider biodiversity community. See the recordings of the *Indigenous Data Provenance, Local Contexts and the Care Principles for Indigenous Data Governance I & II* sessions at Living Data 2025 via this youtube link

<https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PL0jzBCTMHGM1ZJgQgUVSFum061T9IWwa5>.

The writers support the adding of Biocultural notices to type specimen Wikidata items. However they are of the opinion that any Wikidata property proposal for Biocultural Notices should be delayed until infrastructure and supporting documentation has been developed by GBIF and in the TDWG biodiversity data standard DarwinCore. This creation of infrastructure and guiding documentation in GBIF and DarwinCore would provide evidence for the need for the creation of a Wikidata property for Biocultural Notices and would help ensure a successful result for such a property proposal.

Preservation method

Specimen preservation methods vary depending on the type of specimen being preserved. Generally the types of preservation methods include wet preservation such as fish specimens preserved in formaldehyde or alcohol, dry preservation such as pinned insects or herbarium sheets, cryopreservation such bacterial samples preserved in liquid nitrogen and finally plastination of specimens, sometimes used when certain specimens are being prepared for display.

For this data to be added to the type specimen data model a Wikidata property proposal for the preservation method would be required.

Other related links

[WikiProject link](#)

[Wikidata & Wikimedia Commons as Platforms for Scientific Knowledge](#)

[Data model for Natural History specimen images](#)

[Crosswalk link](#)

[Template:Specimen](#)

[Template:Biohis](#)

[Common properties currently in use](#)

Acknowledgements

I would like to express my gratitude to Brodie Satherley, Online Collections Data Analyst at Tāmaki Paenga Hira, Auckland War Memorial Museum, my co-collaborator on the [Wikidata:WikiProject Natural History Specimen Data Model](#). I very much appreciate of all the help and contributions made by her to inform this documentation.